

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates: 29 January - 31 March 2023

Report published: January 2025

**The frontline of conservation:
Defending the Kenyan Maasai Mara
from biodiversity loss**

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Abstract

Kenya's Northern Mara Conservancies are at the frontline of conservation. As more landowners have joined the conservancies, they have committed to removing fences, halting the construction of permanent structures and crop farming, and using rangeland management techniques to manage grazing to benefit both livestock and wildlife.

Biosphere Expeditions ran a citizen science research expedition in three adjacent Northern Mara Conservancies: Ol Choro, Mbokishi and Enonkishu, from January to March 2023. Ol Choro is Kenya's oldest conservancy, formed in 1992; Mbokishi is one of the newest and is currently transitioning from a predominantly livestock-grazed area into a conservancy; Enonkishu has been a conservancy since 2014.

The expedition carried out extensive wildlife monitoring via vehicle transect surveys, foot patrol surveys, waterhole surveys, opportunistic recordings of iconic mammal and bird species, and camera trapping. Studies were conducted by citizen and professional scientists, working closely with rangers from each conservancy and training them to continue wildlife monitoring themselves after the expedition.

Biosphere Expeditions ran similar research expeditions in Enonkishu in 2019 and 2020, establishing ongoing wildlife monitoring, which was still successfully being run in 2023. The 2023 expedition therefore focussed its efforts in Ol Choro and Mbokishi, neither of which had implemented formal wildlife monitoring regimes prior to the expedition. As such expedition also established baseline data for these two conservancies.

The results gave a clear picture of significantly greater abundance and diversity of wildlife in Enonkishu and Ol Choro than in Mbokishi. There was no significant difference in wildlife abundance or diversity between Enonkishu and Ol Choro.

Changes in wildlife between 2019 and 2023 in Enonkishu were variable, but an overall fall in abundance across all species was recorded. An analysis of cattle vs buffalo distribution showed partial sharing of grazing areas by these species, with no clear difference between Ol Choro and Enonkishu (no buffalo were recorded in Mbokishi).

The foot patrol survey methodology revealed a variety of wild animals visiting areas close to settlements in Ol Choro and Mbokishi, with evidence of a greater abundance nearer to settlements than further way, for some species including herbivores such as zebra and wildebeest as well as some predators such as hyaena.

The main waterhole surveys showed a substantial difference between Ol Choro and Mbokishi, with the Ol Choro waterhole dominated by wild animals and the Mbokishi waterhole dominated by livestock. There was little evidence of resource competition at either waterhole.

The opportunistic surveys of specific mammals and birds, along with the use of hotspot camera traps, confirmed the greater abundance of wild species in Ol Choro and Enonkishu compared to Mbokishi. These surveys also revealed the presence of notable species such as elephant and hyaena in all conservancies.

Key recommendations are proposed to continue monitoring for the three conservancies. These include continuing wildlife monitoring, equipping rangers with the capacity, equipment and skills to carry out monitoring, introducing new management techniques to benefit wildlife in Mbokishi and introducing range land management techniques to benefit both wildlife and cattle grazing.

The expedition was discontinued when it became clear that local host Collection In the Wild and their Eco Camp property were solely interested in maximising profit over citizen science conservation efforts.

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1. Expedition review

Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per [Karimi & Hammer \(2019\)](#). The expedition focused on monitoring wildlife and biodiversity of Mbokishi Conservation Area and Ol Choro Oiroua, while continuing established monitoring activities in Enonkishu Conservancy. The expedition undertook six types of monitoring activities across a range of taxa: vehicle line transects to record large mammals in a standardised manner that contributes to long-term monitoring; ‘mammal mapping’ and ‘raptor mapping’ to cover spatial distribution of specific species within the project area; waterhole monitoring to identify species most reliant on water; foot patrols near human settlements identifying evidence of mammal presence and proximity; and camera trapping using an established grid system as well as monitoring areas with above average mammal activity (so-called hotspot monitoring). The project contributes to the Northern Mara Conservancies’ vision to create resilient and economically viable conservancy systems and strategies that lead the way in biodiversity conservation and defend the Mara from settlement and agricultural encroachment, poaching and destruction.

1.2. Dates and teams

The project ran over a period of two months divided into four 13-day groups, each composed of a team of international citizen scientists, a professional scientist, local research liaison and an expedition leader. Group dates were as shown in the team list below. Dates were chosen to coincide with the most favourable weather in the Mara although the dates for the final group extended into the start of the wet season.

The expedition team was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

29 January - 10 February 2023: Nadine Andrews (UK), Jan Behrendt (Switzerland), Katharina Behrendt (Switzerland), Stanlynn Daugherty (USA), Evelyn Frey-Royston (Germany), Graham Hill (UK), Nicole Hoagland (USA), Jenny Holland (UK), Catriona Logan (UK), Rick Royston (Germany), Brad Styner (Canada), Yvette Styner (Canada).

12 - 24 February 2023: Inge Becker-Boost (Germany), Dr. Ingulf Becker-Boost (Germany), Joerg Boysen (Germany), Stanlynn Daugherty (USA), Angelika Krimmel (Germany), Sylvia Lawson-Brown (UK), Alistair Luckham (UK), Sanjay Mellacheruvu (USA), Agam Mellacheruvu (USA), Andrea Rohlf (Germany), Verena Thuerey (Germany), Stefan Thuerey (Germany), Vatsala Vadapalli (USA).

26 February - 10 March 2023: Ralf Bürglin (Germany, journalist/blogger, see [coverage](#)), Stephen Crowther (UK), Isabelle Fragniere (Switzerland), Robyn Gray (USA), Matthias Herold (Germany), Andreas Herold (Germany), Michael Hodgson** (USA), Birgit Käser (Germany), Steven Neely (USA), Nicolas Thobois (France), Oscar Thobois (France), Maria Thobois (France), Elisa Velez-Thobois (France).

19 - 31 March 2023: Lukas Bausch (Germany), Khanti Challa (Netherlands), Maya Geis (Germany), Neil Goodall (UK), Tatjana Gröger (Germany), Mandanna Hurfar (Germany), Jana Lippmann (Germany), Tim Schniebs (Germany), Alex Smith (UK), Betsy Snow (USA), Peter Snow (USA), Donna Walters (USA).

Throughout the expedition: Johnny Adams (expedition leader), Roland Arnison (expedition scientist), Rebekah Karimi (local project manager and science adviser). Also: Dr. Matthias Hammer (founder & executive director of Biosphere Expeditions) during the setup phase and for part of group 1.

Medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place throughout the expedition and had to be invoked once for a minor head injury, which required stitches, with the casualty making a full recovery.

Figure 1.2a. A 2023 expedition team. © Tim Schniebs.

1.3. Partners

Biosphere Expeditions' two main partners for this expedition are the Mara Training Centre and Enonkishu Conservancy. The Mara Training Centre was built with the objective of training conservancy members within the Mara on enhancing their ecological knowledge of cattle husbandry and pastoralism. Enonkishu Conservancy, a local association dedicated to the protection of the environment and its resources, was created to preserve wildlife in tandem with ancient Maasai cow-herding culture.

1.4. Acknowledgements

We are very grateful to all the expedition citizen scientists, who not only dedicated their spare time to helping but also, through their expedition contributions, funded the research. We would also like to thank our key partners, Enonkishu and Mbokishi manager Lawrence Mbelati and rangers Francis Dapash, Albert Cheruiyot, Nonyuat Lenkume, Meshack Chepuret, Mike Koriata, Salami Koriata, Paul Tikoishi Kaelo, Sikona Francis, Jackson Parmari Nchoe, Duncan Ronko, Kipailo Nampaso, Manchau Koros. Ol Choro's warden, Wilson Senteu was instrumental in organizing logistics along with rangers Saruni Njapit, Benson Maitai, James Oyie, Maxon Taanyak, Tyson Nkurrumwa, and Dicskon Simorei. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank members of the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions and donors for their sponsorship, as well as Tarquin Wood for his help in making the expedition a reality. Last but not least, thanks to the team at the Wild Hub: James Maina, Charles Ndirangu, Benard Cheruiyot, Kenneth Kigen, Alvin Chesingei, Cyrus Ngeno, Nelson Leina, Kennedy Kipkurui, Jacklin Naisiai, Josephine Kapei, Joan Leshan, and Paul Langat for looking after us and keeping us well fed.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org. Enquires should be addressed to Biosphere Expeditions at the address given on the website. Also available are:

All expedition reports, including this and previous expedition reports:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Expedition diary/blog:

<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/kenya-2023/>

2. Introduction

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The Conservancy concept was initiated as one of the solutions to stop the increasing losses of wildlife populations in Kenya outside the parks, where previously a large proportion of wild animal species were to be found. The conservancies create new areas of protected habitat exclusively for wildlife on additional land adjoining the existing parks and reserves. However, this cannot be done unless the communities who own the land to be set aside as wildlife conservancies can derive income and benefits from allowing this to happen which match or exceed alternative forms of land use. The establishment of the conservancies in Kenya has been the single most successful conservation initiative since the creation of national parks in the 1940s. Conservancies protect land for Kenya's wildlife and, even more importantly create sanctuaries of safety. In addition conservancies bring benefits in the form of direct payments and jobs to the people who share the land with wildlife. As more landowners join conservancies, they commit to removing fences, halting the construction of permanent structures and crop farming, and grazing their livestock to allow room and resources for wildlife. During the past decade, many of the people living in the area have experienced human-wildlife conflict in the form of livestock predation. The growth of the Mara conservancies northward will benefit members who have often borne the costs of human-wildlife conflict.

2.1. Study Area

Figure 2.1a. Location of the study area within Kenya (in red circle).

The Mara-Serengeti ecosystem (MSE) within Kenya contains 24 conservancies, in addition to the Maasai Mara National Reserve (MMNR). Four of these conservancies in the northern Mara have an agreement to share accessed land with tourism partners in those areas.

Within the Mara conservancies, land is leased from the local Maasai landowners. They prioritise conservation by limiting development and committing to a system of livestock grazing and wildlife conservation. The north-western boundary of Ol Choro Oirouwa and Enonkishu conservancies is the Mara River, forming a natural border between wildlife habitats and smallholder farms, and communities across the river (Trans-Mara).

The study area for the 2023 expedition (Figure 2.1a) included three of the Northern Mara Conservancies: Enonkishu, Ol Choro Oirouwa, and Mbokishi Conservation Area (Figure 2.1b). The expedition focused on monitoring wildlife and biodiversity of Mbokishi Conservation Area and Ol Choro Oirouwa, while continuing established monitoring activities in Enonkishu Conservancy (Karimi & Hammer 2019, Lee et al. 2020). Ol Choro and Enonkishu are established conservancies, Mbokishi is relatively new.

Figure 1.1b. The study area, showing the three conservancies, settlements and other relevant locations.

Adjacent to Enonkishu Conservancy is Mbokishi Conservation Area, which was registered in 2021. Mbokishi covers 7,332 acres, with 80 members from over 15 different families. Enonkishu and Mbokishi have been jointly managed since 2022. Six rangers were hired prior to the introduction of the current manager, and although two have been sent for ranger training, their skill set varies as they are working in a new area. Mbokishi is currently a mixed use conservation area, with much of it utilised for livestock grazing, although nearly 1,000 acres have always been managed for conservation. Mbokishi has the potential to expand, as it demonstrates positive conservation initiatives to attract more funding. In 2023, its main source of funding came from a three-year agreement with PlatCorp Foundation as a Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) project, with the objective of removing fences and establishing a tourism product that can bring in its own revenue in the future.

The study area also included the village of Munyas, to the north and continuous with Mbokishi Conservation Area. For simplicity, Munyas is included in Mbokishi for the purposes of this research.

The expedition team was based in the [The Wild Hub](#) on the north border of Enonkishu (Figure 2.1b).

2.2. Background

Biosphere Expeditions first initiated a wildlife monitoring regime within Enonkishu Conservancy in 2019 (Karimi & Hammer 2019) and continued this in 2020 (Lee et al. 2020), before the COVID-19 epidemic made expedition impossible in 2021 and 2022. Since 2019, the Enonkishu ranger team has consistently been collecting monthly wildlife data, showing the effectiveness of the 2019 and 2020 expeditions at training local rangers. Because of this and requests by neighbouring conservancies to repeat the process with their staff, the 2023 expedition expanded neighbouring areas, where wildlife monitoring has been sporadic or absent. Basic monthly monitoring in Enonkishu was still supported by Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists during the expedition, but the majority of efforts was directed to neighbouring Ol Choro and Mbokishi. The comparison of old and new within a similar landscape allowed us to quantify differences in wildlife populations within each construct, while also collecting baseline data from a new conservation area.

Mbokishi still has many fences within its boundaries, which vary in effectiveness. The plan is to remove these fences, which will impact wildlife populations. As such, the baseline data collected by the 2023 expedition will help to evaluate how effective future measures are at re-establishing wildlife and wildlife corridors in Mbokishi.

The differences in livestock grazing within Enonkishu and Ol Choro offer another opportunity for comparison. Within Enonkishu, the entire conservancy is divided into grazing blocks, and cattle are used to stimulate vegetation growth and attract more wildlife. Within Ol Choro, there are both grazing and wildlife zones, and the livestock is not on a rotational grazing plan. Ol Choro is starting a sustainable rangeland management regime – the data collected for this report will provide a baseline before this regime is implemented.

Aside from the wildlife area in Mbokishi (Enonmbokishi), grazing of livestock is largely uncontrolled and occurs throughout the settlement areas. Human-wildlife conflict is an increasing concern with the establishment of the conservation area. The vehicle transects conducted in Mbokishi recorded livestock not within a fence or boma, and if herds were with a herder or grazing without supervision. Management can use these data to build capacity within the community, especially as the area becomes more wildlife-friendly. There are mitigation techniques to minimise human-wildlife conflict, including supervising livestock as they graze.

The baseline data from Mbokishi is an important missing piece within most of the Mara conservancies, as none had implemented a wildlife monitoring regime prior to re-establishing wildlife habitat. A vehicle transect is the most efficient way to cover as much ground as possible within the given timeframe, but much of the wildlife within Mbokishi settlements is not visible during the day. Members and rangers of Mbokishi insist there is plenty of wildlife in the area. Because of the uncertainty of vehicle transects detecting wildlife, we also utilised a scat survey around bomas housing livestock at night to detect evidence of wildlife, specifically where mammals were not being seen. An additional tool used during the expedition was to place hotspot cameras near the homes of Mbokishi rangers, who could then monitor them and ensure they would not be stolen or tampered with.

African savannahs are undergoing management intensification and managers are increasingly challenged to balance the needs of large mammal populations with the maintenance of vegetation and ecosystem diversity (Asner et al. 2009). Sustainably protecting Africa's natural areas requires information on the efficacy of large-scale management decisions, but often neither experimental treatments nor large-scale responses are available for analysis (Asner et al. 2009). Wildlife managers in poorer African nations often struggle with conflicting demands of anti-poaching activities (including rangers' salaries and vehicle costs) and helping local communities to build health clinics and schools on the borders of reserves. More often than not, wildlife monitoring is treated as a luxury carried out by foreign researchers, but not important enough to take money and manpower away from other important managerial functions (Caro 2016).

In the northern Mara, constant wildlife monitoring is required, especially given the interface with nearby human settlements. The results of wildlife population movements are used to advise management decisions so that livestock and wildlife can coexist. Given the component of ecotourism to the financial model that sustains the conservancy, monitoring and reporting on wildlife is required: ecotourism is more likely to be successful with greater large mammal biodiversity.

Wildlife monitoring throughout the 2023 expedition included vehicle transects, waterhole monitoring, spoor surveys around settlement areas, hotspot camera trap placement, and opportunistic recording of charismatic birds and mammals throughout the study area.

3. Methods

The methodologies used in the previous Biosphere Expedition in Enonkishu in 2020 (Lee et al. 2020) were used in 2023, with some adaptations made, as described below. The foot survey methodology was also introduced in the 2023 expedition to investigate the identity and diversity of wild animals in the vicinity of villages.

One of the outcomes of the previous expeditions was the training of the Enonkishu rangers in continuing the wildlife surveys after the end of the expedition. For this reason, the 2023 expedition research was largely focused on the neighbouring conservancies of Ol Choro and Mbokishi, with some research work carried out in Enonkishu to support the rangers there. The Enonkishu rangers used their experience to help train the 2023 citizen scientists.

Most of the research involved the citizen scientists, accompanied by local rangers wherever possible, recording animal sightings and associated observations using customised projects on the CyberTracker app (Steventon et al. 2011). CyberTracker is a software that allows customised recording of information via a smartphone app, designed with wildlife monitoring in mind. The customised CyberTracker projects were uploaded onto citizen scientists' smartphones (various models) and also, in groups 3 and 4, onto four Huawei tablets provided by Biosphere Expeditions for this purpose. The records collected on the CyberTracker projects was later downloaded wirelessly to a laptop. Some of the research methodologies required the recording of tracks or waypoints, as described below. For groups 1 and 2, this was carried out using Garmin ETrex20 GPS units. The use of these units in the field was found to be problematic and time-consuming, hence they were replaced by using the Gaia GPS app on smartphones and tablets, in groups 3 and 4. QGIS software was used to create the maps in this report.

3.1. Mammal population monitoring using fixed vehicle transects

Five vehicle transects were established at the start of the expedition, chosen to survey a range of habitats across Ol Choro and Mbokishi. Citizen scientists also helped Enonkishu rangers survey the five vehicle transects that were established by the 2019 expedition (Karimi and Hammer 2019) and used by the rangers every month since then. Details of the transects used on the 2023 expedition are shown in Table 3.1a and Figure 3.1a below.

Table 3.1a. Summary of vehicle transects.

Area	Transect	Distance (km)
Ol Choro	OC T1	13.9
Ol Choro	OC T2	14.1
Ol Choro	OC T3	12.2
Mbokishi	MB T1	12.4
Mbokishi	MB T2	15.6
Enonkishu	T1	7.0
Enonkishu	T2	11.3
Enonkishu	T3	4.6
Enonkishu	T4	3.3
Enonkishu	T5	4.2

Figure 2.1a. Map of vehicle transect routes.

Transect monitoring was conducted from vehicles. Citizen scientists, together with rangers, used binoculars, smartphones or tablets with the CyberTracker app, rangefinder and protractor to record all animals observed. Observers sat or stood in the bed of a double cab Toyota Hilux with a metal cage. The driver of the vehicle drove slowly (<20 km/h) along the transect route, waiting for a signal from the observers in the back of the truck when a group of animals was spotted. Target animals included all medium to large mammals and ostriches. Livestock animals (cattle, sheep, goats, donkeys) were also recorded. Humans and dogs were only recorded if they were herders accompanying livestock. Livestock, humans and dogs were only recorded if they were in areas generally accessible to wildlife (i.e. not within fenced enclosures).

The GPS location, date and time were automatically recorded on CyberTracker, while observers entered the species, age and sex composition (if known), group size, general behaviour and habitat type. Perpendicular distances were measured as the shortest distance from the transect to the original position of the centre of the group of animals; where a perpendicular measure could not be measured, then an angle between 0 (vehicle trajectory) and 90 degrees (perpendicular to the vehicle) was recorded to allow later recalibration of distances accordingly. The location of each observed animal sighting was

later calculated, for the purposes of mapping, based on the observer's location, the distance between the observer and the animal(s), the angle between the vehicle direction and the animal(s) from the observer, and the bearing of the vehicle direction. The bearing of the vehicle direction was not recorded at the time, but was later modelled as the bearing between the vehicle locations recorded for each two consecutive sightings.

For each transect, total distance was recorded (in kilometres to the closest 100 m) using the tracking function of a Garmin eTrex 20 GPS unit or Gaia GPS app on a smartphone. The weather (air temperature, approximate wind level, approximate cloud cover / extent of rain) was also recorded at the start and end of each transect.

Figure 3.1b. Teams carrying out vehicle transects.

3.2. Foot surveys near settlements

Foot surveys were carried out near settlements in Ol Choro and in Mbokishi to assess indirect evidence of wildlife in these areas where direct observations of wild animals was less common. These settlements generally comprised a boma for the livestock, houses for a few families and various fenced areas for food growing.

The foot surveys involved walking in areas around specific settlements, recording the presence of footprints and scat of wild animals and using a CyberTracker project (Figure 3.2a). Various methods were used to identify species from these signs:

- A ranger, with knowledge of local wildlife, accompanied the citizen scientists in all cases
- The foot survey teams used portable guides to footprints and scat of Kenyan wild animals
- For any signs that were not readily identifiable in the field, photos were taken and/or samples of scat were collected, for later identification in the classroom using reference books.

The duration and distance walked for each foot survey were recorded as a measure of field effort, along with track recording on a GPS unit or app.

The methodology in groups 1 and 2 involved simply walking randomly around locations near settlements, recording evidence of each unique species and some indication of the abundance of this evidence. The results from this methodology revealed the presence of specific animals in these areas, with a subjective indication of abundance.

The methodology was improved for groups 3 and 4 to provide a more consistent and replicable approach with more meaningful results:

- Settlements with unfenced land around them were chosen where possible
- The team walked around the settlement up to three times at different distance bands from the outer fence of the settlement (0 to 25 metres, 25 to 50 metres and 50 to 100 metres).
- In each of these bands, the team recorded every sighting of scat or footprints of wild animals, as far as was practical, to give a consistent method of recording abundance.

Figure 3.2a. Team on a foot patrol survey.

3.3. Waterhole surveys

Waterhole observations were carried out to identify how animals use waterholes in different conservancies. This included any resource competition for access to the water and a general survey of animals from specific observation points in different conservancies (Hayward & Hayward 2012, Ogutu et al. 2010).

Each waterhole survey comprised:

- Consecutive shifts (2 or 3 hours) of teams recording animals seen from a vehicle parked next to the waterhole, from 06:00 to 20:00.
- At five minute intervals, records were made on a CyberTracker app of all animals seen (including livestock, humans and also vehicles) up to 800 meters away from the waterhole.
- The species, number of individuals, general behaviour, age and sex composition (if known) and distance between the animal(s) and the waterhole were recorded. The weather conditions were also recorded for each sighting recorded.
- During the first and last shifts, red light torches were used to identify animals in the absence of daylight.

This methodology included recording the same animals repeatedly over time (e.g. if an animal stayed near the waterhole for more than five minutes), thus giving an indication of waterhole use through the day rather than a direct count of animal numbers. Various water holes were surveyed in this way in groups 1 and 2. By groups 3 and 4, only two waterholes (Kuluo and Munyas) were surveyed, to build up a larger and more reliable dataset for these two waterholes.

Table 3.3a. Summary of how many times waterholes were surveyed.

Waterhole name	Conservancy	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Total
"Dam"	Mbokishi	1	0	0	0	1
Mustafa	Enonkishu	0	1	0	0	1
Munyas	Mbokishi	0	1	1	1	3
Kuluo	OI Choro	1	0	1	1	3

Figure 3.3a. Locations of waterholes surveyed.

Figure 3.3b. Waterhole survey at Kuluo.

3.4. Iconic species mapping

A list of mammals of particular interest for the conservancies was produced, including nocturnal mammals (not recorded on the day time vehicle transects), animals likely to attract tourists and locally rare mammals. The list of these mammals is shown in Table 3.4a. The list includes ostrich (despite not being a mammal) as it is a large, ground-based animal that is relatively rare in the three conservancies. The inclusion of 'Other' as a species allowed citizen scientists to record other mammals that they considered to be relevant for this research objective, that were not on the list.

Table 1.4a. List of iconic mammals targeted in Mammal Mapping.

Aardvark	Elephant	Serval
African Civet	Greater Galago	Slender Mongoose
African Palm Civet	Honey Badger	Spotted Hyaena
African Wild Dog	Leopard	Springhare
Buffalo	Lesser Galago	Striped Hyaena
Bushpig	Lion	White Rhino
Caracal	Marsh Mongoose	White-tailed Mongoose
Cheetah	Ostrich	Zorilla
Common Genet	Other	
Crested Porcupine	Pangolin	

Mammal mapping was carried out by citizen scientists on an ad-hoc basis: usually when driving to and from more formal research tasks. Any iconic mammal seen at these times was recorded on the Mammal Mapping CyberTracker project. This approach allowed a large proportion of the three conservancies to be surveyed almost daily over the eight weeks of the expedition.

The GPS location, date and time were recorded, while observers entered the species, age and sex composition (if known), group size, general behaviour and habitat type. The distance between the observer and the animal(s) (measured using a Rangefinder) was recorded, as well as the bearing (measured by compass) to the animal(s) from the observer. This is a different angle measurement than the one used in the Vehicle Transect methodology, which used the angle in relation to the vehicle direction, not a compass bearing.

To avoid double counting, iconic species observed while on a vehicle transect were recorded in the transect data and not in the Mammal Mapping data.

Around two or three night drives per group were carried out to record nocturnal mammals. Each night drive lasted around 1.5 hours and involved a small team including a ranger, equipped with red light torches, driving around a variety of habitats and recording all iconic nocturnal mammals seen. The sightings were recorded on the Mammal Mapping CyberTracker app, but omitting recording distance and angle to animal. For practical reasons, these night drives were largely carried out in Enonkishu.

Figure 3.4a. An elephant recorded on 'Mammal mapping'.

3.5. Raptor mapping

Similar to the Iconic Mammal Mapping methodology, a list of specific birds of interest (mostly raptors) was produced, in collaboration with the Mara Raptor Project¹ as shown in Table 3.5a. The methodology to identify and record sightings of these birds was referred to as 'Raptor Mapping'.

Table 3.5a. List of bird species targeted in Raptor Mapping.

African Crowned Eagle	Fish Eagle	Red footed Falcon
African Marsh Harrier	Gabar Gowshawk	Ruppell's Vulture
Amur Falcon	Grey crowned-crane	Secretarybird
Augur Buzzard	Lanner Falcon	Sparrow Hawk
Bat Hawk	Lappet-faced Vulture	Tawny Eagle*
Bateleur	Long-Crested eagle	Verreux's Eagle
Southern Ground-Hornbill	Martial Eagle	Western Banded Snake Eagle
Black-chested Snake-eagle	Montagu's Harrier	White-backed Vulture
Black-shouldered Kite	Other	White-headed Vulture
Brown Snake Eagle	Peregrine Falcon	Wahlberg's Eagle
Dark Chanting Goshawk	Pygmy Falcon	

¹ <https://www.kenyabirdofpreytrust.org/mararaptorproject>

Eight bird species were of particular interest to the Mara Raptor Project, due to their precarious conservation status in the Mara region (Figure 3.5a).

Figure 3.5a. Priority bird species for the Mara Raptor Project.

Raptor Mapping was also carried out by the citizen scientists on an ad-hoc basis, as with Mammal Mapping. Any of the listed birds seen at these times by any team was recorded on the Raptor Mapping CyberTracker app.

The same variables were recorded by the smartphones and entered by the citizen scientists as with Mammal Mapping. For birds in flight, the distance and bearing was omitted, due to them being difficult to measure and not greatly meaningful data to record.

Bird species were identified using a mixture of citizen scientists' and rangers' knowledge, identification images provided by the CyberTracker app, and field guides. Often, identification was carried out through discussion amongst the team in the field. When identification was in doubt, often one of the team took photographs for more confident identification from more resources in the classroom later.

Grey crowned cranes *Balearica regulorum* were of particular interest as this species is categorised as endangered (Mirande & Harris 2019), but appears to be relatively common in Enonkishu conservancy. Due to its size and appearance, this bird is also easy to identify by citizen scientists.

Figure 3.5b. Grey crowned cranes.

As the Raptor Mapping methodology was carried out in groups 1 and 2, it became apparent that many bird sightings recorded as Tawny Eagle *Aquila rapax* were being recorded, likely erroneously in many cases due to the difficulty of differentiating this species from other similar brown birds, such as some species of kite *Milvus spp.* To address this, additional training was given for groups 3 and 4, alongside the addition of a ‘confidence level’ field in the Raptor Mapping CyberTracker app.

3.6. Camera traps

The expedition had the use of eight Bushnell “Essential E3” camera traps with lockable metal protection boxes, as hotspot cameras.

The aims of deploying these cameras were:

- Collecting evidence of the presence of animals, to complement the other methodologies and monitor species continually day and night over long periods of time.
- Investigating the range of animals that visit key locations (see below).
- Recording any notable animal behaviour, undisturbed by human presence.

Cameras were placed at selected locations and subsequently serviced (batteries and/or SD cards replaced), removed, or re-located throughout the expedition on an ad-hoc basis. The camera locations were often recommended by rangers, selected on the basis of:

- Clear animal trails
- Sites with signs of habitual use by species of interest (e.g. trees favoured by leopards)
- Animal carcasses
- Locations within 200 metres of settlements in Mbokishi (due to low abundance of observed wildlife in these areas)

The cameras were generally fixed on a tree, at approximately one metre above the ground and approximately two metres away from the point of interest. Cameras were usually set to take three consecutive photographs, day and night, with sensor level set to 'auto' or 'low', and interval set to five seconds. For some animal carcasses, a second camera, set to record videos, was placed alongside the camera set to take photographs.

Each camera (and each SD card) was reused many times during the expedition. The duration that any given camera was kept in a location was determined partly by the likelihood of it capturing images of animals and partly by the teams' research schedules and hence opportunity to visit the camera's location.

The hotspot cameras used on the expedition complemented the longer-term camera trap grid methodology already used in Enonkishu and Ol Choro by their rangers. The Biosphere Expedition team helped the rangers to service their camera trap grids during the duration of the expedition.

Figure 3.6a. Team setting up a camera trap.

4. Results

4.1. Vehicle transects

Field Effort

All vehicle transects were attempted or completed several times per expedition group, spread evenly throughout the two weeks for each group. On a minority of occasions, a transect was attempted, but not completed. Reasons for this included running out of time, vehicles getting stuck in mud (especially in group 4 due to the start of the rainy season) or needing to abandon the transect to avoid getting stuck.

When transects were not fully completed, an effort was made to complete it the following day. In some cases, longer transects were intentionally split into two halves, with a different team driving each half at the same time to complete the whole transect between them.

The table below shows the effective number of times that each transect was fully completed, allowing for the sum of each case of partial completions of transects. A total of 4,007 records of animal sightings were made.

Table 4.1a. Transect counts and distances.

Transect	Transect length (km)	Total distance covered (km)	Effective number of times completed
EN T1	7.0	45.4	6
EN T2	11.3	58.7	5
EN T3	4.6	30.0	6
EN T4	3.3	20.7	6
EN T5	4.2	26.9	6
MB T1	12.4	148.7	12
MB T2	15.6	208.9	13
OC T1	13.9	238.7	16
OC T2	14.1	188.0	13
OC T3	12.2	156.3	12
Total Enonkishu	30.4	182	29
Total Mbokishi	28	358	24
Total OI Choro	40.2	583	41
GRAND TOTAL	98.6	1122	95

Table 4.1a shows that the Enonkishu transects were completed fewer times than the transects in OI Choro and Mbokishi. This reflects the purpose of the expedition to support the Enonkishu rangers in their monthly schedule of transects, while carrying out a more intensive research for the baseline surveys in OI Choro and Mbokishi.

Abundance and spatial analysis of wild and domestic animals

Figure 4.1a. Transects sightings by group size: domestic and wild animals.

Figure 4.1a shows the total counts of animals observed on transects over the whole expedition. The number of counts shown is weighted towards those transects carried out more often (Table 4.1a) and so Figure 4.1a does not give an accurate comparison of animal density between different areas (see Figure 4.1c). Figure 4.1a shows the extent of wildlife and livestock cohesion, irrespective of the timing of the cohesion, across the study area.

Figure 4.1a shows that Mbokishi is the only conservancy with very clear lines between livestock and wildlife locations, with few wildlife sightings in the most intensive livestock areas (east Mbokishi and north Munyas). This differs from Enonkishu and Ol Choro, which have been managed for wildlife to a greater extent.

Enonkishu and Ol Choro both show greater integration of wild animals and livestock. The spatial distribution also shows a similar density of wild animal sightings in livestock-grazed areas as in non-livestock-grazed areas, which suggests low resource competition between livestock and wild animals in these two conservancies.

Figure 4.1a shows little between Ol Choro and Enonkishu wildlife cohesion that could be attributed to the more regulated grazing plan at Enonkishu.

Figure 4.1b. Comparison of numbers of wild animals vs domestic animals recorded across the three conservancies.

Figure 4.1b shows a clear correlation between age of conservancy and the number of wild animals compared to livestock. In the more established conservancies, there were more observations of wildlife than of livestock.

Figure 4.1c gives a more detailed comparison between conservancies of species sighted. The data is expressed as number of animals sighted per km of transect, to allow meaningful comparison.

The number of species (giving a measure of species diversity) sighted in each conservancy was: 17 in Mbokishi, 23 in Enonkishu, and 29 in Ol Choro.

The charts show a significantly lower number of animals and a lower species diversity in Mbokishi compared to the other two conservancies. Notably, Mbokishi had no sightings of buffalo, hippopotamus or Grant's gazelle.

There are some clear differences between Ol Choro and Enonkishu of species sighted. Of the more populous species, impala were more common in Enonkishu whereas Thomson's gazelle were more common in Ol Choro. Bush duiker, bush hyrax, elephant, lion, spotted hyena, and ostrich were all seen in Ol Choro but absent in Enonkishu. A smaller number of species were present in Enonkishu, but absent in Ol Choro (bat-eared fox and bushpig).

Figure 4.1c. Numbers of wild animals sighted per km of transect, by species and conservancy.

Changes in species abundance and diversity in Enonkishu

Table 4.1b compares transect data from the 2019 expedition with the 2023 transect data. The same transect lines were used in both years, at similar times of the year, although the 2023 expedition involved driving along the transects fewer times than in 2019, so total transect distance is less in 2023.

Table 4.1b. Changes in species abundance and richness in Enonkishu, 2019 to 2023.

	2019	2023	% change
Total transect surveys distance, km	241	182	-25%
Number of species counted	24	23	-4%
Number of animals counted per km	35.1	24.7	-29%

Figure 4.1d shows the changes between 2019 and 2023 by species, from the same sets of transect data.

Figure 4.1d. Changes in species abundance in Enonkishu, 2019 to 2023, by species.

Species richness in Enonkishu was broadly the same between the two years, but species abundance showed a significant decline from 2019 to 2023. This was especially true for the grazing herd species, notably eland (-91%), zebra (-60%), warthog (-46%), Thomson's gazelle (-37%), impala (-34%), and topi (-34%). There were, however, increases in the abundance of hartebeest (+165%), Grant's gazelle (+57%), wildebeest (+56%), waterbuck (+47%) and buffalo (+16%).

These changes in species' abundance may partly be accounted for by the natural movements and population dynamics of herd animals. The overall 29% decrease of all recorded animals is likely to be due to the apparent increase in large predators that prey on herd animals between 2019 and 2023, noted through anecdotal evidence. The fact that the greatest wild animal losses were for those that were most numerous in 2019, and that those that are typical prey species for large cats, adds weight to the hypothesis that greater predation by lions, leopards, and cheetahs is a key factor in the decrease.

The evidence for an increase in large predators from the transect data alone is limited. Leopard abundance did increase by 165% between 2019 and 2023, but no lions were seen on Enonkishu transect surveys in either year, despite rangers claiming that lion sightings had become much more frequent. Predators at the top of the food chain are often surveyed through collaring (to track movements) or camera traps utilising mark-recapture methodology. The same methodology is not used to estimate prey abundance because the densities of predators in a healthy ecosystem will always be lower than the densities of prey species, so differences in predators and prey cannot be analysed. Therefore, the limited data collected is not indicative of an absence of large predators in the area, in 2019 or 2023. However, research by the Mara Predator Conservation Programme showed an increase in lion density in Enonkishu Conservancy from 2021 to 2022 (Mara Predator Conservation Programme 2023).

Lions and cheetahs were sighted in Enonkishu in 2023 and recorded through the Iconic species methodology (see below), and from camera trap surveys. but there is no equivalent data set from 2019 to compare this with, primarily because field effort on the incidental sightings was not recorded.

4.2. Foot surveys

Field Effort

Thirty-two foot surveys were successfully carried out, almost all in OI Choro and Mbokishi (Appendix 1). A number of additional foot surveys were carried out by group 1, in which the data was lost due to teething problems with data transfer from the CyberTracker app (not shown in Table 4.2a).

For each foot survey, the conservancy, the area name, and the name of the individual settlement / boma / manyatta that the research team walked around (if a name could be provided by the ranger) were recorded. The total distance walked on the foot surveys was 50.4 km.

With the exception of one survey (Oiti, 17/02/2023), each track walked was recorded on a GPS device or phone app. This record gave the distance walked data, an indication of the geographical area covered by the walk and the extent to which the team (in groups 3 and 4) was successful in surveying the three distance bands around each settlement, as intended. Figure 4.2.a shows all the recorded tracks, to give an indication of the spread of areas covered by the foot surveys.

The total distances walked across all walk surveys were 27.0 km in Mbokishi foot patrols and 23.4 km in OI Choro foot patrols.

A breakdown of all foot surveys completed is shown in Appendix 1.

Figure 4.2a. Recorded tracks of foot surveys.

Figure 4.2b and c show a selection of foot survey tracks recorded in OI Choro and Mbokishi, to highlight the difference between the 'roaming' approach used by groups 1 and 2 and the concentric distance bands used by groups 3 and 4. These maps also show the difficulty groups 3 and 4 teams had in walking around Mbokishi settlements, compared to settlements in OI Choro. The reasons for this were largely due to fence layouts and patches of impenetrable bush around Mbokishi settlements.

Figure 4.2b. Selection of recorded tracks of foot patrols in Ol Choro.

Figure 4.2c. Selection of recorded tracks of foot patrols in Mbokishi.

Species recorded by scat and footprints

The scat or footprints of 34 species of wild animals were recorded from all the foot patrols (Mbokishi 29 species, Ol Choro 23 species). The list of these species is shown in Figure 4.2d, which shows the relative abundance of evidence of each species by evidence type.

Figure 4.2d. Number of records of wild animals by scat, footprints and other evidence from foot patrols.

The species recorded most are those who appear to be comfortable near to human settlements. The largest number of records were for herd species that are common in the conservancies: zebra, wildebeest, Kirk’s dik-dik, and impala, although high numbers of hippopotamus and spotted hyaena were also notable.

Some species were easier to identify than others from their scats or footprints, even with the help of the local guide accompanying each foot patrol. The species that were notably difficult to identify (e.g. genets; honey badger) tended to be the species with relatively few counts. The counts of scats vs footprints recorded varied by species but were broadly similar in total: 4.9 counts of footprints per km compared to 6.2 counts of scats per km, across all species.

The data shows differences in counts of scats and footprints for some species between Mbokishi and Ol Choro settlements (Figure 4.2e). More evidence of hippopotamus was seen in Ol Choro, which can be accounted for by the close proximity of the Mara River to these settlements. More evidence of elephants was seen in Mbokishi than in Ol Choro. In total, 26% more counts of scats and footprints per km were recorded in Ol Choro compared to Mbokishi.

Table 4.2.2a. Foot patrol summary comparison between Ol Choro and Mbokishi.

	Absolute counts			km walked	Per km walked		
	Scat counts	Footprint counts	Total		Scat counts	Footprint counts	Total
Ol Choro	109	152	261	20.9	5.2	7.3	12.5
Mbokishi	186	82	268	27.0	6.9	3.0	9.9
Total	295	234	529	47.9	6.2	4.9	7.8

The results need to be treated with some caution due to the difficulty of clear identification of many species (especially in the case of small mammals and similar size antelope species) and due to inconsistencies between research teams in recording the number of footprints or scats, when finding large numbers in one location.

However, some clear results seen from the above chart are:

- A wide range of species were evidenced on the foot patrols, indicating that these animals were present near to bomas
- Broadly, a similar number of species were evidenced in each conservancy
- Evidence of elephants was more prevalent in Mbokishi, whereas evidence of impalas, civets, and hippos was more common in Ol Choro.

Figure 4.2e. Number of records of wild animals from foot patrols: comparison by Conservancy.

Species by distance from settlement

The methodology was adapted from group 2 onwards to record the distance (in bands) from the nearest settlement fence for each record of a scat or footprint (Table 2.4a).

Comparisons of scat and footprint records by distance from a fence are only meaningful where the field effort for each distance band can be allowed for. An analysis of a subset of the foot patrol data is shown below to make these comparisons. The subset contains only records from foot patrols that involved approximately the same distance walked in each distance band (specifically foot patrols that involved walking around settlements in two or three concentric circles).

Table 4.2a. Evidence of wild animals from subset of six foot patrols with comparable distance bands.

DISTANCE BAND:	PER KM WALKED		
	Less than 25 m	25 to 50 m	50 to 100 m
African Civet	13.9	4.3	1.5
Banded Mongoose	1.5	2.1	
Bat-eared Fox		1.1	0.7
Black-backed Jackal		1.1	0.7
Cape Hare		1.1	0.7
Caracal		1.1	0.7
Elephant		1.1	
Giraffe		7.5	2.9
Hippopotamus	10.8	5.3	10.3
Impala	10.8	8.5	8.1
Kirk's Dik-dik	9.3	8.5	1.5
Olive Baboon		1.1	0.7
Spotted Hyaena	13.9	6.4	2.9
Springhare	3.1	3.2	1.5
Thomson's Gazelle	1.5		0.7
UNCERTAIN	4.6		
Wild Cat	3.1		
Wildebeest	20.1	8.5	5.9
Zebra	52.5	35.2	16.2
Grand Total	145.0	96.0	55.2

Njapit 23 March 'Boma 1' (Ol Choro)

Njapit 24 March 'Manyatta' (Ol Choro)

Njapit 5 March 'Manyatta' (Ol Choro)

Njapit 1 March 'Njapit Family' (Ol Choro)

Munyas 3 March 'Rönko/Dennis'
(Mbokishi)

Oiti 1 March 'Jackson Nchoe' (Mbokishi)

KEY

- African Civet
- Banded Mongoose
- Bat-eared Fox
- Black-backed Jackal
- Cape Hare
- Caracal
- Elephant
- Giraffe
- Hippopotamous
- Impala
- Kirk's Dik-dik
- Olive Baboon
- Spotted Hyaena
- Springhare
- Thomson's Gazelle
- Wild Cat
- Wildebeest
- Zebra

Figure 4.2f. Aerial views of the subset six foot patrols with tracks walked and location of scats and footprints by species.

The subset of foot patrol data comprises six foot patrols which have similar distances walked for the 0 to 25 m and 25 to 50 m distance bands in each case; three of these six foot patrols also involved a similar distance walked for the third distance band (50 m to 100 m away from the settlement fence) in each case.

Future use of the foot patrol methodology should include measuring the distance walked in each distance-from-fence band (as well as the total transect distance), to enable simpler and more accurate analysis of the results.

The data from the subset of foot patrols shown in Table 4.2a show counts of evidences per km walked. The distance of each concentric circle walked in the surveys was estimated from the recorded tracks for each survey to allow comparison of evidences per km walked, by band.

The table reveals a pattern of significantly more evidences of animals nearer to the settlements than further away, for almost of all the species. This pattern may seem counter-intuitive and there is little published literature on the topic, but the phenomenon of wild animals being attracted to the areas adjacent to bomas is known to many rangers and local people. The reasons for this are likely to differ depending on the species. Spotted hyaena may be attracted to the settlements by the possibility of prey in the form of the cattle in the boma. Conversely, prey animals such as zebra, impala, and wildebeest may have a tendency to congregate near settlements as a protection against lion attacks, on the basis that lions have an aversion to hunting near human settlements

4.3. Waterhole observations

Field Effort

Eight waterhole surveys were carried out, surveying four waterholes, with two waterholes (Munyas and Kuluo) surveyed three times each. Each survey involved teams recording sightings over fourteen hours (from 06:00 to 20:00). The combined field effort totals 122 hours.

Table 4.3.1a. Summary of waterhole surveys completed.

Waterhole name	Conservancy	Total	Survey hours
"Dam"	Mbokishi	1	14
Mustafa	Enonkishu	1	14
Munyas	Mbokishi	3	42
Kuluo	OI Choro	3	42
Total		8	112

The surveys at “Dam” and Mustafa were only carried out once each. The Mustafa survey began at 08:00, as the first shift that day was carried out at another waterhole (Nabaala) which was found to be dry, so the survey was moved to Mustafa instead. For these reasons, the “Dam” and Mustafa waterhole surveys are not included in the following analyses, although the raw data exists.

Munyas vs Kuluo comparison

Figures 4.3a-d compare the data from the Munyas (Mbokishi) and Kuluo (Ol Choro) waterholes. Data are shown as total number of animals sighted in each case. This is not a total count of individuals, but a count of all animals seen at every five minute interval: hence all individual animals that stayed within sight of the observer for ten minutes or more were counted repeatedly. Therefore, the ‘animal count’ data are a measure of both the absolute number of individual animals and the length of time they spent within sight of the waterhole.

Figures 4.3a & b compare all sightings for Munyas vs Kuluo (wild animals in Figure 4.3a and domestic animals in Figure 4.3b). Because this analysis includes all sightings of animals up to 1,000 m from the waterhole, it is essentially a point survey covering all ground visible from the survey vehicle parked next to the waterhole, rather than a survey of the animals that make use of the waterhole itself.

Figure 4.3a. Counts of all wild animal sightings from Kuluo and Munyas waterholes.

Figure 4.3.2b. Counts of all domestic animal sightings from Kulo and Munyas waterholes.

Figures 4.3a & b show the clear predominance of wild animals near Kulo waterhole and domestic animals near Munyas waterhole, corroborating the conclusion made from the transect surveys. However, the counts of cattle at the two waterholes were similar, suggesting that the presence of cattle does not in itself preclude the presence of wild animals, especially in the case of Thomson’s gazelle, wildebeest and zebra.

A similar analysis was carried out to show data for only animals sighted within five metres of the waterhole: this represents animals that are attracted to the waterhole as a resource. Figures 4.3c & d show this analysis for notable wild and domestic species seen within five metres of the waterhole, displayed as percentages of all animals (i.e. animals seen at any distance, as shown in the previous two charts). No domestic animals were sighted within five metres of the water at Kulo waterhole.

Figure 4.3c. Wild animal sightings within five metres of the water at Kulo and Munyas waterholes, as percentage of all animal sightings.

Figure 4.3d. Domestic animal sightings within 5 metres of the water at Munyas waterhole, as percentage of all animal sightings.

Figures 4.3c & d show that the Kulo waterhole is likely a meaningful resource for buffalo, but not for any domestic animal. Conversely, the Munyas waterhole appears to be a significant resource for domestic animals, but not for wild animals.

There were only 45 occasions when animals were actually witnessed drinking at water holes: the total number of animals seen drinking on these occasions is shown in Table 4.3b.

Table 4.3b. Counts of animals seen drinking at waterholes, wild vs domestic animals.

	Kulo	Munyas
Wild animals	266	8
Domestic animals	0	551

Only three species of wild animals were seen to drink at Kulo waterhole: buffalo, wildebeest, and zebra. The only wildlife witnessed drinking at Munyas waterhole were eight zebra on one single occasion.

In interpreting these figures, it should be noted that the wild animals choose when to visit the waterhole to drink, whereas the domestic animals are led there by a herder.

It is clear that very few wild, but many domestic animals (notably cattle and goats) were seen drinking at Munyas, with the converse pattern at Kulo.

Temporal analysis and resource competition

Figures 4.3e & f show the pattern of wildlife sightings within 20 metres of the waterhole, through the hours of 06:00 to 20:00 of all three survey days for each waterhole. The X-axis of each chart only includes the times (five minute intervals) for which there are records of at least one animal sighted. These two charts are shown to give some indication of potential resource competition between wild and domestic animals.

Figure 4.3e. Kuluo waterhole animal counts within 20m of water over three survey days.

Figure 4.3f. Munyas waterhole animal counts within 20m of water over three survey days.

This confirms that there were very few sightings of domestic animals within 20 metres of Kuluo water hole and very few sightings of wild animals within 20 metres of Munyas waterhole.

This clear result suggests significant resource competition, to the extent that wild animals largely avoid Munyas waterhole possibly because of its use by the domestic animals throughout much of the day. However, there is no direct evidence that wild animals are suffering from lack of water due to any resource competition: all three conservancies have a number of waterholes that in all likelihood provide sufficient water for both wild and domestic animals; it appears that wild and domestic animals (and their herders) simply favour certain waterholes.

There were no occasions when wild animals and domestic animals were seen together at the same time within 20 metres of either waterhole.

4.4. Iconic species mapping

Field effort

As iconic species mapping was carried out opportunistically by citizen scientists, there is no precise measure of field effort. As an indication, however, the citizen scientists spent time looking for the iconic species whenever they were driving through the conservancies, but not actively engaged in transect or waterhole surveys. This field effort for daytime iconic species mapping is estimated as 224 hours across the whole expedition².

The results shown are for iconic species recorded both on transects and from the time spent specifically on opportunistic iconic species mapping.

Iconic species sightings

Figures 4.4a-e show the locations and group sizes of iconic species recorded both on transect surveys and from the opportunistic iconic species mapping methodology. The maps show the locations of the animals (calculated using the method described in Section 3.1), not the location of the observer. Many more animals were recorded on transect surveys than during iconic species mapping and so the spatial distribution is weighted towards the areas visible from the transect lines.

The maps show a significant presence of iconic animals, with both ecological and economic (tourism) importance, in Enonkishu and Ol Choro. Very few sightings were recorded in Mbokishi.

Large cat predators were more common in Enonkishu than in Ol Choro. Lions were also regularly seen and heard by rangers and staff in the Wild Hub in Enonkishu in February, but this evidence was not formally recorded.

Hyaenas were more common in Ol Choro and in Enonkishu and ostriches were seen only in Ol Choro.

² Estimated two hours per team per active day; average 3.5 teams per active day; Eight active days per group; total four groups.

Figure 4.4a. Iconic species diurnal sightings excluding buffalo.

Figure 4.4b. Lion, cheetah and leopard sightings.

Figure 4.4c. Hyaena sightings.

Figure 4.4d. Elephant sightings.

Figure 4.4e. Ostrich sightings.

Buffalo and cattle

Comparisons of buffalo and cattle spatial distributions are especially important as there is a potential for competition for grass between these two species. Reducing this competition would involve careful management of cattle grazing and grass growth (Herrick et al. 2023).

Tables 4.4a & b show data comparing buffalo and cattle sightings from transect records only. Note that that average group size for buffalo (Table 4.4a) is mathematically correct, but may appear misleading: buffalo family herd counts were typically 40 to 70 animals, but the inclusion of sightings of small bachelor herds and lone males (group sizes of one to three) reduces the overall average group size figure.

Buffalo group sizes and total animals were both significantly smaller than the same metrics for cattle. Mbokishi had many cattle and no buffalo sightings. Ol Choro had fewer cattle and more buffalo than Enonkishu: this suggests the possibility of resource competition between the two species.

Table 4.4a. Summary of cattle and buffalo sightings on transect surveys: all conservancies.

	Cattle	Buffalo
Number of sightings	272	77
Number of animals	16,679	1417
Average group size	61.3	18.4

Table 4.4b. Cattle and buffalo numbers per km on transect surveys: comparison between conservancies.

	Cattle	Buffalo
Enonkishu	18.6	1.5
OI Choro	13.8	2.0
Mbokishi	15.3	0.0

Figure 4.4f shows the spatial distribution of buffalo and cattle sightings from transect data and iconic species mapping across the three conservancies, with weighted towards the areas visible from transect lines. This map shows little cohesion between cattle and buffalo in Enonkishu and OI Choro. No buffalo were recorded in Mbokishi, indicating zero cohesion. The small extent of cattle-buffalo cohesion in Enonkishu and OI Choro at least partly confirms the phenomenon known to herders of buffalo being attracted to an area shortly after cattle have left.

Figure 4.4f. Buffalo and Cattle sightings.

Night drive sightings

Night drives were carried out opportunistically and predominantly in Enonkishu. There was no precise measure of field effort, but an estimated 21 hours were spent on 14 night drives over the course of the expedition.

The range and abundance of nocturnal species seen on these night drives is shown in Figure 4.4g.

Figure 4.4g. Numbers of animals and number of sightings recorded on night drives, by species.

4.5. Raptor mapping

Field effort

As with iconic species mapping, raptor mapping was carried out opportunistically, with no precise measurement of field effort available. Citizen scientists recorded any sightings of the listed birds seen at any time during their active research days, including during vehicle transects.

Abundance and richness

Figure 4.5a shows the number of birds recorded, excluding records made with low confidence in species identification (records labelled as confidence level 2 or below). Nineteen species were recorded, as well as a number of unlisted species recorded as 'Other'. The majority of the sightings comprised one or two individual birds. A minority of species were seen in bigger groups, notably grey crowned crane (maximum group size 28) and white-backed vulture (maximum group size 15).

Figure 4.5a. Number of birds recorded through Raptor Mapping, by species.

The tawny eagle data should be treated with caution: it became apparent that identification of this species was often difficult, with likely confusion with similar size brown birds, such as kites. Even those tawny eagle sightings recorded with a confidence level of 3 and above (or no confidence level recorded) may not be correct identifications. Identification of other birds with low numbers of sightings should also be treated with caution, due to the risk of misidentification by individual citizen scientists.

The results show the presence of seven of the eight species of interest to the Mara Raptor Project: secretary bird, lappet-faced vulture, white-backed vulture, bateleur, martial eagle, and tawny eagle. Of particular significance is the record of a single white-headed vulture (Figure 4.5b) scavenging on an impala carcass (along with other vulture species) in Enonkishu. This is the first recorded sighting of this vulture species in this area; the nearest known white-headed vulture nest is in the Masai Mara Wildlife Reserve. The grey crowned crane, a species classed as endangered, was regularly recorded through the Raptor Mapping.

Figure 4.5b. Photo of white-headed vulture recorded on Raptor Mapping.

Location of sightings

The number of raptor sightings were similar in Ol Choro and Enonkishu (Figure 4.5c). They were significantly lower in Mbokishi, but with a notable cluster of sightings around Munyas (north of Mbokishi).

Figure 4.5c. Map of iconic bird mapping: all sightings.

Grey crowned cranes were seen at several locations in Ol Choro and Enonkishu, as well as around Munyas (Mbokishi) (Figure 4.5d). Especially high group sizes were seen in the border between Ol Choro and Enonkishu.

Figure 4.5d. Map of grey crowned crane sightings.

Bateleur and secretary bird sightings were relatively widespread in Ol Choro and Enonkishu; Martial eagle sightings were largely in Ol Choro, with a few in Enonkishu and Mbokishi. Lappet faced vulture sightings were rare and were in Ol Choro and Enonkishu; the single white headed vulture sighting was in Enonkishu. White backed vultures were a little more common, involved larger group sizes (up to 15 birds in a group), and were in Ol Choro and Enonkishu. Vulture sightings recorded through Raptor Mapping were absent in Mbokishi, although vultures were evidenced in Mbokishi using camera traps.

Figure 4.5e. Map of bateleur sightings.

Figure 4.5f. Map of lappet-face vulture sightings.

Figure 4.5g. Map of martial eagle sightings.

Figure 4.5h. Map of secretarybird sightings.

Figure 4.5i. Map of white-backed vulture sightings.

Figure 4.5j. Map of white-headed vulture sightings.

4.6. Camera traps

Field effort

Hotspot camera traps were placed at thirty locations (Figure 4.6a) for varying periods of time depending on the nature of the location and the practicalities of access for each camera. Six of the camera traps were in the vicinity of the Wild Hub: these cameras were used for several days to check for the presence of lions around base camp, as part of a risk management strategy.

Figure 4.6a. Locations of hotspot camera traps.

The cameras captured 8,232 photographs and 1,130 videos that included animals. Many more images were captured that did not include any animals and were therefore deleted. The two cameras that were set to record videos were each placed alongside another camera, pointing at the same location and set to take photographs. The photographs were intended to identify the species while the videos were intended to give a greater insight into animal behaviour.

Species recorded

Figure 4.6b gives a list of all species of wild animals (including notable bird species) recorded on the camera traps over the duration of the expedition, with a record of how many camera trap locations each species was recorded at.

Figure 4.6b. Species captured on hotspot camera traps: all cameras (244 camera trap nights).

A selection of the photos taken by the hotspot camera traps is given in Appendix 2.

Species recorded near settlements

Four cameras were placed within 100 metres of occupied buildings at the Wild Hub and three cameras were placed within 100 metres of two settlements in Mbokishi, all in order to investigate the presence of wild animals near settlements. The range of species captured on these cameras are shown in the following Figures 4.6c & d.

Figure 4.6c. Species captured on three hotspot cameras near settlements in Mbokishi (total 68 camera nights).

Figure 4.6d. Species captured on six hotspot cameras around Wild Hub, Enonkishu (total 14 camera nights).

The results from the Mbokishi settlement camera traps (Figure 4.6c) are not directly comparable with those from around the Wild Hub (Figure 4.6d) due to the difference in the total camera trap nights in each case. However, the results do suggest a smaller variety of animals, especially diurnal species, near settlements compared to those recorded by the full network of hotspot cameras (Figure 4.6b). Allowing for the smaller number of camera trap nights around the Wild Hub compared to the Mbokishi settlements, the results also suggest a more limited range of wild animals near Mbokishi settlements than around the Wild Hub.

Notable animal behaviour

Figure 4.6e. Camera trap fixed in front of spotted hyaena carcass.

A fresh spotted hyaena carcass was discovered in Mbokishi on 16 Feb 2023. The cause of death was unknown, but not clearly predation. Camera traps recorded the species visiting the carcass and their behaviour over the period 16 February to 1 March 2023, both while the carcass remained in place and at the carcass site after the remains were dragged away. The species and their behaviour is given in Table 4.6a. A distinction is made between those animals investigating and smelling the carcass, and those that were recorded definitively scavenging (eating) the carcass.

The leopard and the hyaenas visiting at night looked in the direction of the camera lens repeatedly, suggesting that they could see the low glow infrared lights.

Table 4.6.4a. Notable animal behaviour at spotted hyaena carcass over time.

Activity with hyaena carcass in place

In the first few days, the carcass was up to 75% covered in maggots and later flies: these largely disappeared after ~5 days. The vultures visited the carcass for ~45 minutes on one occasion (18 Feb). A leopard, hyaena and dogs were recorded rubbing themselves in the carcass.

The carcass was removed from its position in front of the cameras by a scavenging hyaena.

Animals investigating / smelling carcass

- White tailed mongoose
- Back backed jackal
- Marabou stork
- Dogs
- Leopard
- Hammerkops
- Civet
- Bushpigs (one adult with three piglets)

Animals scavenging carcass

- Black kites
- Tawny eagles
- White backed vultures
- Spotted hyaenas (only occasional scavenging: largely investigation only)

Activity at site of carcass after carcass removed

Animals recorded investigating and smelling the site where the carcass had been were:

Black backed jackal, spotted hyaena (including rubbing itself on the carcass site), civet, hammerkop (collecting fur), cattle, dogs, bushpigs (3 adults with 3 piglets)

5. Discussion

The 2023 expedition in Kenya involved a considerable research effort made possible by the time given by fifty citizen scientists over eight weeks.

A clear conclusion from much of the data is that Mbokishi, an area that has not been predominantly managed for wildlife to date, still has a good range of wild animals, concentrated in its western area, where there are much fewer cattle grazing. Having said this, Mbokishi unsurprisingly had fewer wild animals overall and a lower wild animal diversity compared to the Ol Choro and Enonkishu Conservancies. The areas near Mbokishi settlements with the most intense cattle grazing were especially low in wild animal numbers and diversity.

The expedition provided a set of baseline data on wild animals, gathered using a scientific approach, and within the first year of Mbokishi becoming a conservancy. This is the first known instance of a conservancy in the Northern Mara gathering such data. It is important that Mbokishi managers use this resource and continue to monitor in future years.

The expedition provided another significant boost to the management of Mbokishi and Ol Choro by training rangers in the techniques of monitoring wildlife, using practical and repeatable approaches.

The expedition also contributed evidence of particularly rare species in the three conservancies, that previously had no or few records. This included the definitive presence of a white-headed vulture in Enonkishu and camera trap records of bush pigs in Mbokishi.

The lack of cohesion between cattle and wild animals in areas with less strict cattle grazing regimes is very clear in Mbokishi. There was also a notable lack of buffalo sightings in this area. Results from the transect data and the buffalo vs cattle analysis in Enonkishu and Ol Choro do not provide strong evidence of increased cohesion due to the stricter cattle grazing regime in Enonkishu. However, this regime is relatively new and data collection over the coming years may begin to show an increased effect on wildlife-cattle cohesion.

The comparison of wildlife in Enonkishu between 2019 and 2023 showed a significant reduction in wildlife numbers (especially for grazing animals) and a small reduction in species richness over time. It is difficult to draw meaningful conclusions from only these two datasets, as wild animal populations naturally fluctuate over time and space. However, the (anecdotal) increase in predators (i.e. lions) is likely to be a major factor. It should also be noted that many species, including wildebeest and buffalo, showed an increase in numbers over this time period.

The large dataset of wildlife records, especially from the transect methodology, in Ol Choro and Mbokishi provides a valuable baseline record for these areas before they introduce new management regimes. In the case of Mbokishi, as conservation measures are initiated, there is significant potential for wildlife to occupy many of those areas because of the existing wildlife populations and the connectivity with more established conservancies.

The foot patrol surveys in Ol Choro and Mbokishi revealed considerable evidence of a variety of wild animals near to settlements, with no significant distinction in numbers of species evidenced between these two conservancies. There were some teething problems with this methodology, which were partly resolved during the expedition and could be further improved as suggested below. In particular, the approach taken to recording the number, density and age of the large numbers of footprints and scats of herd animals was not always consistent. However, the foot surveys were useful as a basic methodology to note the presence of particular animals, with at least some indication of abundance. The foot surveys also revealed at least indicative negative correlation between wild animal abundance and distance from bomas for many species including zebra, wildebeest, impala and hyaena (showing greater abundance nearer to bomas).

The waterhole observations at Munyas (Mbokishi) and Kuluo (Ol Choro) confirmed the considerably higher abundance of wildlife in Ol Choro compared to Mbokishi. These observations functioned as both point surveys of the surrounding land and as surveys of the use of the waterholes themselves.

The Munyas waterhole was used for drinking almost exclusively by livestock; the Kuluo waterhole was used exclusively by wild animals. There was no evidence of livestock preventing wild animals accessing water or vice versa. There were very few cases of wildlife and livestock animals both being within 20 metres of a waterhole during the same time period. The conclusion from this is that wildlife and livestock have a tendency to avoid each other at or near water holes and that they each have sufficient access to water, either at the waterholes being monitored or at other waterholes.

The iconic mammal mapping showed a widespread distribution of a range of animals of significance for conservation and tourism, across much of Ol Choro and Enonkishu, with relatively few sightings in Mbokishi. This confirms the conclusions that Mbokishi has a poorer abundance and diversity of wild animals than the other two conservancies. The significance of ostriches being regularly sighted only in Ol Choro is unknown: it may simply be that the large areas of grassland in Ol Choro offer particularly suitable habitats for this territorial animal. However, local knowledge suggests that the ostrich sightings were of two groups known to frequent areas in Ol Choro, with one of those groups frequently seen in Enonkishu but not sighted during the transect surveys there.

The raptor mapping revealed the presence of several species of conservation interest across all three conservancies, including seven of the eight birds of interest to the Mara Raptor Project. As with other wildlife evidence, Mbokishi had significantly fewer sightings of most of the raptor species compared to Enonkishu and Ol Choro. Notably, the raptor mapping had no sightings of secretarybirds or any vulture species in Mbokishi. The camera trap records did however show the presence of vultures in Mbokishi, feeding on a carcass.

The hotspot camera traps provided evidence of a large number of animal species across the three conservancies. This included many species not evidenced through any of the other methodologies, such as bushpigs, marabou stork, and vultures in Mbokishi, and white-bellied bustards in Ol Choro. Camera traps also bolstered the evidence of key predators (lions and leopards) not easily evidenced through the other methodologies. These results confirm the benefits of using hotspot camera traps.

The camera traps were also used to investigate the range of wildlife very close to bomas (complementing the foot patrol analysis) in Mbokishi and the Wild Hub (Enonkishu). The images captured on these cameras confirmed the presence of a number of animals in each case, notably hyaena and Kirk's dik-dik near to Mbokishi settlements, as well as hyaena, genet, civet and lion near to the Wild Hub. A total of only ten species of wild animal were recorded near to two settlements in Mbokishi (over a total of 68 camera trap days), likely confirming the previous conclusions of relatively low wildlife diversity in Mbokishi, rather than the influence of proximity to a boma.

The key clear conclusions from the 2023 expedition are that Mbokishi has a significantly lower wildlife abundance and diversity than Enonkishu or Ol Choro. This is almost certainly due to the predominant land management practices focussed on livestock. Furthermore, the differences between Enonkishu and Ol Choro in wildlife diversity and abundance are much less clear.

The impact of the introduction (a decade ago) of more sophisticated rangeland management techniques in Enonkishu, intended to benefit both cattle and wildlife, is not directly evident from this research. It is likely that a much longer time period (allowing time for the new management techniques to have an effect and allowing for year-to-year wildlife population fluctuations) will be needed before a meaningful analysis can be made. However, it is notable that the analyses made in this report do suggest broadly similar wildlife abundance and diversity in Enonkishu and Ol Choro, despite Ol Choro having a 31-year history as a wildlife conservancy compared to Enonkishu's 10 years.

The lack of clear conclusions on the effect of rangeland management techniques on wildlife and livestock emphasises the importance of continuing a consistent scientific monitoring regime in all three conservancies for years to come.

Addendum (by Matthias Hammer, Executive Director, Biosphere Expeditions)

The Kenya expeditions came to an end, because our local hosts at Enonkishu ([Collection In The Wild](#) and their [Eco Camp](#) property) never understood that citizen scientists working for and in partnership with the conservancy are not safari tourists with whom profits can be maximised at will.

There were constant attempts by the hosts to increase contractually agreed prices and invent new charges. In the end our hosts even actively reneged on a contractual obligation for accommodation in 2024, because they were able to get more money from another customer.

Since focus on maximum profit is not a model that Biosphere Expeditions wishes to operate under, we reluctantly had to end the expedition.

We explicitly thank all rangers and other staff, who had nothing to do with profit-maximising efforts, for their support and commitment to the project. We are pleased to have played a part in training them in survey techniques and hope these efforts will continue into the future.

6. Recommendations

1. ENONKISHU

- a. Continue the monitoring regime established by Biosphere Expeditions in 2019, along with continued use of the rangeland management techniques aimed at benefitting both livestock and wildlife.
- b. Use the data presented in this report as an additional insight into the wildlife dynamics in Enonkishu.

2. OL CHORO

- a. Maintain ongoing monitoring similar to that used by Biosphere Expeditions in 2023, but less frequently, to make valuable recommendations and lessons for land management, benefitting both livestock and wildlife and gaining an insight into changes in wildlife patterns over time.
- b. Use the data presented in this report as an insight into the wildlife dynamics in Enonkishu and as a baseline for future monitoring.
- c. Prioritise equipping rangers and staff with monitoring equipment and the capacity to collect and maintain data integrity throughout the year.

MBOKISHI

- a. Continue the plan to develop new management techniques to benefit wildlife, including halting clearing and crop agriculture, removing fencing, and subscribing to a grazing plan.
- b. Maintain ongoing year-round monitoring similar to that used by Biosphere Expeditions in 2023, but less frequently, to make valuable recommendations and lessons for land management, benefitting both livestock and wildlife and gaining an insight into changes in wildlife patterns over time.
- c. Use the data presented in this report as an insight into the wildlife dynamics in Mbokishi and as a baseline for future monitoring.
- d. Prioritise equipping rangers and staff with monitoring equipment and the capacity to collect and maintain data integrity throughout the year.

3. ALL CONSERVANCIES

- a. Transect surveys: record the compass bearing to the animal sighting as well as the angle between the track and the animal sighting (as done in the current methodology). This would allow more accurate presentation of results using GIS software: an improvement on the need for a calculation used in this 2023 analysis to calculate the location of the animal sighted.
- b. Foot patrol survey methodologies would be improved by:
 - i. Recording the distance walked within each distance band as well as total distance per walk.
 - ii. Devising a more consistent approach to recording the number of scats and footprints in cases where these are encountered in high numbers (e.g. herd animals).
- c. Waterhole monitoring should be extended to other dams and water sources, particularly the more remote water sources, to continue investigation into the extent of resource competition during the dry season.
- d. Communicate results from research with the communities who have devoted their land to conservation to build understanding on how human-wildlife conflict can be mitigated.

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8. Appendices

Appendix I: Summary of foot surveys completed.

Group	Date	Conservancy	Area	Settlement name	Distance walked (km)
Group 1	01/02/2023	OI Choro	Njapit		4.10
	01/02/2023	Mbokishi	Oiti		2.36
Group 2	17/02/2023	OI Choro	Njapit		2.70
	17/02/2023	Mbokishi	Oiti		3.50
	19/02/2023	Mbokishi	Munyas		3.70
	19/02/2023	OI Choro	Njapit		0.59
	19/02/2023	OI Choro	Njapit		1.70
	21/02/2023	Mbokishi	Munyas		0.21
	21/02/2023	OI Choro	Njapit		2.50
	23/02/2023	Mbokishi	Oiti		2.20
	23/02/2023	Mbokishi	Oiti		1.00
	Group 3	01/03/2023	Mbokishi	Oloringan	Jackson Nchoe
01/03/2023		Mbokishi	Oloringan	Koros	0.51
01/03/2023		Mbokishi	Oloringan	Shunkur	0.53
01/03/2023		OI Choro	Njapit	Njapit family	3.00
03/03/2023		Mbokishi	Oloisa	Saitolok Oloisa	0.71
03/03/2023		Mbokishi	Oloisa	Rönko/Dennis	0.69
03/03/2023		Mbokishi	Oloisa	Danronko	0.20
05/03/2023		OI Choro	Njapit	Manyata	2.40
05/03/2023		Mbokishi	Oloringan		1.50
05/03/2023		Mbokishi	Oloringan		0.34
07/03/2023		Mbokishi	Munyas		3.00
07/03/2023		Mbokishi	Oloisa	Saitolok Oloisa	0.70
Group 4	23/03/2023	Mbokishi	Kaelo		0.80
	23/03/2023	Mbokishi	Kaelo		0.20
	23/03/2023	OI Choro	Njapit		2.10
	24/03/2023	Mbokishi	Oloisa	Ronko	0.90
	24/03/2023	Mbokishi	Oloisa	Sapania	1.70
	24/03/2023	OI Choro	Njapit	Manyatta	1.80
	28/03/2023	Mbokishi	Munyas		0.20
	28/03/2023	Mbokishi	Munyas		0.45
	28/03/2023	Mbokishi	Oloisa	Sapania	0.50

Appendix II: Selection of camera trap images.

